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Research Article

**PERIODONTAL DISEASE AND VARIOUS SOURCES OF
CHEWING STICKS**¹Mudasir Maqbool, ²Dr. Aashir Jamal, ³Roshaan Mohi ud din Rathore¹Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences, University of Kashmir,²Allied Hospital Faisalabad³University College of Medicine and Dentistry Lahore**Article Received:** January 2020 **Accepted:** February 2020 **Published:** March 2020**Abstract:**

Periodontal disease is a bacterial disease-causing dental plaque. This causes swollen, bleeding gums, signs of gingivitis (the earliest stage of periodontal disease), and loosening of the teeth, a sign of severe periodontitis (the advanced stage of disease). Maintaining good oral hygiene and visiting dentist regularly (about once every six months, or more often if we have gum disease) can prevent periodontal disease. Oral cavity harbors a diverse and abundant number of complex oral pathogens causing different oral diseases. The development of dental caries and periodontal diseases has been found to be closely associated with several gram-positive and gram-negative microorganisms. Removal of dental plaque is effective in treating gingivitis, preventing periodontal disease and dental caries. Toothbrushing is the most common method used to remove plaque. However, toothbrushes are rare in many third-world countries, where locally available chewing sticks are commonly employed for maintaining dental hygiene. Chewing stick is an easily affordable oral hygiene device. Various Chewing sticks have been used by the majority of people in different parts of world. In this review, we will briefly discuss periodontal disease and various sources of chewing sticks.

Key Words: Oral hygiene, Periodontal disease, Miswak.

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INTRODUCTION:

Periodontal disease refers to an inflammatory disease of the supporting tissues of the teeth caused by specific microorganism or group of specific microorganisms, causing progressive destruction of the periodontal ligament and alveolar bone with pocket formation, recession or both. It is one of the most common chronic inflammatory diseases that affect the tissues surrounding the teeth¹. Gingivitis is a milder form of periodontal disease that causes redness and swelling (inflammation) of the gingiva. Although Gingivitis is localized only to the gingiva without causing any harm to periodontal tissues, gingivitis can progress to serious gum disease called periodontitis. Periodontitis is a severe form of periodontal disease and leads to inflammatory changes in the gingival epithelium, periodontal membrane, dental cement and alveolar bone. However loss of connective tissue and alveolar bone by periodontitis could lead to the loss of teeth. The prevalence of periodontitis is more than 50% of the adult population in the current world².

Healthy gums have a coral pink color. Gum line hugs teeth tightly with no bleeding. In gingivitis, gums bleed easily when brushed or when probed gently during an examination. Gums are inflamed and sensitive to touch, possibly producing bad breath and bad taste appearing bluish-red in color between the teeth. In Early Periodontitis, gums may begin to pull away from the teeth. Bleeding, puffiness, and inflammation become more pronounced giving bad breath, and bad taste. Slight loss of bone can be seen horizontally on X-ray. Pockets of 3-4mm between teeth and gums are also seen in one or more areas of the mouth. In Moderate Periodontitis, gum boils or abscesses may get formed. Teeth look longer as gums begin to recede and front teeth may begin to drift, showing spaces with bad breath and bad taste too. Both horizontal and angular bone loss is visible on X-ray is visible. Pocket between teeth and gum range from 4-6mm deep. Bacterial plaque is not the sole factor leading to disease. Etiologic attribution reveals that 20% of bacterial infection, 50% of genetic variance and rest 20% of tobacco use contribute to the disease. This disease has multi-factorial etiology including microbial ecology, host susceptibility and mucosal immunity. Risk factors that can affect the onset of periodontitis, rate of progression, severity of periodontitis, and the response to therapy can be classified into Non-modifiable risk factors and Modifiable risk factors³.

The oral micro-organisms involved are: the periodontal pathogens, for example, *Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans* (previously *Actinobacillus actinomycetemcomitans*), *Prevotella gingivalis*, and *Bacteroides forsythus* (*Tannerella forsythia*)^{4, 5, 6}.

Although these periodontal pathogens form a part of the normal residential micro-flora in the oral cavity, when the ecological balance among them is disturbed, this might favor the initiation, establishment and progression of gingival diseases and thereafter, although not always, at unknown time, conversion from gingival to periodontal disease⁵. Cigarette Smoking leads to more plaque formation, more number of harmful bacteria, modified immune response, vascular changes, and direct toxic effect. Smoking is the single major preventable risk factor for causing periodontal disease. The habit can cause bone loss and gum recession even in the absence of periodontal disease. Various studies indicate that smoking and nicotine lead to increase in inflammation by reducing oxygen in gum tissue and triggering an over-production of immune factors called cytokines (specifically ones called interleukins). In excess amount, cytokines are harmful to cells and tissues. In addition, when nicotine reacts with oral bacteria, such as *P. gingivalis*, the effect produces even greater amounts of cytokines and eventually leads to periodontal connective tissue breakdown. Smokers may be more than ten times more likely than nonsmokers to harbor the bacteria that cause periodontal disease, and are also more likely to have severe periodontal disease. The risk of periodontal disease is directly proportional, and increases with the number of cigarettes smoked per day. Smoking cigars and pipes carries the same risks as smoking cigarettes. Exposure to secondhand smoke may also be associated with an increased risk for developing periodontal disease, according to one study. Fortunately, when smokers quit, their periodontal health gradually recovers to a state comparable to that of nonsmokers. Some research also indicates that regular cannabis (marijuana) smoking also increases the risk of periodontal disease⁷.

Periodontal Index (PI)

The Periodontal Index (PI) was developed in the 1950s for the purpose of assessing periodontal disease⁸ and was widely used until the 1980s⁹. Using a light source, a mouth mirror and an explorer rather than a periodontal probe, the PI assessed the periodontal tissue, and was scored as no overt gingival inflammation (0), mild gingivitis (1), gingivitis (2), gingivitis with pocket formation (6), and advanced destruction of the periodontal tissue with tooth mobility and loss of masticatory function (8)^{10, 11}. Development of the Periodontal Disease Index (PDI) was a result of challenges faced by the World Health Organization experts in the assessment of periodontal diseases in Asia¹². The PDI assesses the severity of gingival and periodontal tissue destruction and scores the healthy gingival tissue (G0), mild to moderate gingivitis on part of tooth (G1), mild to moderate

severe gingivitis all around the tooth (G2), severe gingivitis with ulceration (G3), gingival sulcus extending 0–3 mm (G4), and periodontal pockets 3–6 mm and ≥ 6 mm (5) and (6), respectively. The PDI uses the six pre-selected teeth (Ramfjord teeth) rather than the full mouth examination, and the teeth include the maxillary right first molar, maxillary left first central incisor, maxillary left first premolar, mandibular left first molar, mandibular right first central incisor, and mandibular right first premolar sum of tooth scores. The PDI for the individual is the sum of the tooth scores divided by the number of teeth examined. Although the PDI is rarely used today, Ramfjord's teeth continue to be used in many epidemiological studies¹³.

Chewing Stick

Chewing stick or natural toothbrush is called with various names such as Miswak, siwak^{14, 15}. Generally chewing sticks are prepared from arak (*Salvadora perisca*) in geographical areas where it does not grow it is prepared from other plants. Sticks of various trees especially Neem (*Azadirachta Indica*), Zaitoon (*Olea Europaea*), kikar (*Acacia Arabica*), Ban (*Glycosmic Pentaphylla*), Khiran (*Capparis Aphylla*), Meyinro (*Serindeia Warneckei*), Orin Ata (*Fagara Zanthoxyloides*), Ayan (*Distemonanthus Benthamianus*), Pako Ijebu (*Massalaira Accuminata*), Pako dudu (*Anogeissus Leiocarpus*), Ewuro (*Vernonia Amygdalina*), Igi emi (*Bytyrospermum Paradoxum*), Pako pupa (*Terminalia Glaucescens*), Egbo Egbesi (*Nauclea Latifolia*), lime tree (*Citrusauranta Folia*), orange tree (*Citrussinensis*), bitter cola (*Garcinia kola*), Fagara zanthoxyloides, Chaw stick (*Gouania Lupuloides*), senna (*Cassia vinnea*) African Laburnum (*Cassia Sieberianba*) have all been used as chewing sticks. In Bangladesh the following plants are used as chewing sticks Nishinda (*Vitex Negundo*), Neem (*Atzadiracha Indica*), Bely-asra (*Achyranths Aspera*), Bhat (*Clerodendrum Viscosum*), Joytun (*Sesbania Sesban*), Kaminee (*Murraya Paniculata*), Akondo (*Calotropis Procera*), Khejur (*Phoenix sylvestris*), Bohera (*Terminalia Belerica*), Moth-bhringraj (*Wedelia Chinensis*), Batul (*Sapium Indicum*), Olut-kumbal (*Abroma Angusta*), Sheora (*Streblus Asper*) and Motkila (*Glycosmis Arborea*)^{16, 17}. At least 182 plant species are used worldwide in preparing chewing sticks¹⁸. Pencil-sized sticks of various plants of 10–25 cm long with diameter 1–2 cm are prepared from the root, stem, twigs or bark^{19–21}. Miswak has anti-bacterial properties, anti-cariogenic and anti-periodontopathic properties^{22–25} and it releases into saliva substances that may explain its ability to reduce caries and periodontal disease^{26–30}. In animal studies *Salvadora perisca*

has also shown some anti-ulcer as well as anti-inflammatory properties³¹.

CONCLUSION:

A full understanding of the microbial factors, their pathogenicity as well as host factors are of the essential importance for pathogenesis of periodontal disease. In this way it could be possible to treat the periodontal patients adequately. Chewing stick is an affordable oral hygiene device. Natural toothbrush sticks can be used by the vast majority of people. Another advantage is the ready availability in towns or villages. In addition, as it is dry and small size, it is easily carried around, hence enabling the user to prompt use after every meal. The relative accessibility and popularity of chewing sticks in the Middle East and Africa as an oral hygiene tool make it a cost effective agent for plaque control in such communities. Their taste is agreeable and reported to have anti-plaque and many other pharmacological properties.

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